

SIGNIFICANCE OF ENTEROBIASIS AND ITS OCCURRENCE IN CHILDREN OF THE KHOREZM REGION

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Annotation: Enterobiasis is one of the most common helminthic diseases in children. Enterobiasis remains an acute problem for the pediatric population, especially in regions with high population density, limited sanitary conditions, and low hygiene culture. In the conditions of the Khorezm region, where a high level of crowding is observed in children's institutions, the risk of enterobiasis transmission increases. Timely detection and treatment of the disease is important for preventing complications and mass outbreaks.

Keywords: enterobiasis, pinworms, helminthiasis, children, Khorezm, prevention.

Аннотация: Энтеробиоз — одно из самых распространённых гельминтозных заболеваний у детей. Энтеробиоз остаётся острой проблемой детского населения, особенно в регионах с плотной заселённостью, ограниченными санитарными условиями и низкой гигиенической культурой. В условиях Хорезмского региона, где наблюдается высокий уровень скученности в детских учреждениях, риск передачи энтеробиоза возрастает. Своевременное выявление и лечение заболевания имеет важное значение для предотвращения осложнений и массовых вспышек.

Ключевые слова: энтеробиоз, острицы, гельминтозы, дети, Хорезм, профилактика.

Annotatsiya: Enterobioz bolalarda eng ko'p tarqalgan gelmintoz kasalliklaridan biridir. Enterobioz, ayniqsa, aholi zich joylashgan, sanitariya sharoitlari cheklangan va gigiyenik madaniyati past bo'lgan hududlarda bolalar aholisining o'tkir muammosi bo'lib qolmoqda. Xorazm viloyati sharoitida, bolalar muassasalarida aholining yuqori darajada zichligi kuzatilayotganligi sababli, enterobioz yuqish xavfi ortadi. Kasallikni o'z vaqtida aniqlash va davolash asoratlar va ommaviy epidemiyalarning oldini olish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: enterobioz, gijja, gelmintozlar, bolalar, Xorazm, profilaktika.

Introduction

Enterobiasis is a form of helminthiasis of an infectious nature. It manifests as intestinal damage, allergies, and itching of the anal opening. To date, it is the most common form of helminth infestation in Uzbekistan.

The disease is caused by pinworms. These are small, thin worms that settle in the human intestines and actively reproduce there.

Children aged 2 to 10 years are usually affected by this infection. The peak incidence of the disease occurs at the age of 5.

The source of the disease is an infected person. Pinworm eggs settle on bedding, toys, and furniture and are carried by insects. Infection can occur through water, unwashed fruits and vegetables, and even simply by inhaling dust.

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Treatment of helminthiasis is complicated by its resistance to medications and the high probability of autoinfection. Therefore, doctors recommend that parents strictly monitor their child's adherence to personal hygiene rules.

The disease often goes unnoticed for a long time. Some symptoms only appear two weeks after infection with pinworm eggs. The child may experience some discomfort in the form of itching. However, as a rule, egg-laying on the skin around the anal opening occurs at night, and parents do not notice the child's restlessness.

If the initial stage of the disease is left untreated, it progresses, and the itching becomes constant and very severe.

Helminth infection can be suspected by changes in the child's behavior. Appetite may change – either increase or be completely absent, and the child may be bothered by abdominal pain. Invasion can cause vomiting, nausea, and sleep disturbances.

Sometimes, the symptoms of enterobiasis can include a persistent cough, allergic manifestations, dry skin, and even an unprovoked runny nose.

The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of enterobiasis among children in the Khorezm region. The study involved 45 children aged 3 to 12 years.

Materials and Methods:

The examination was conducted among 45 children attending preschool and school institutions in the Khorezm region. The research method was a scraping for pinworm eggs, performed in the morning hours, and clinical manifestations were taken into account (itching in the anal area, restless sleep, scratching). A questionnaire survey of parents was also conducted regarding symptoms and sanitary and hygienic conditions at home.

Results:

Out of 45 children examined, 17 (37.8%) had confirmed cases of enterobiasis. The highest infection rate was observed among children aged 4–7 years. The majority of infected children showed characteristic symptoms, including nocturnal itching and irritability.

Research Results:

Age group	Number of children	Number of infected	Percentage of infected (%)
3–5 years old	15	8	53,3
6–8 years old	15	5	33,3
9-12 years old	15	4	26,7
Total	45	17	37,8

Discussion:

The results of the study show a high prevalence of enterobiasis among young children. The highest infection rate was found in the 3–5 year age group, which is associated with insufficient adherence to personal hygiene, frequent contact, and shared items.

It should be noted that the presence of symptoms (anal itching, restless sleep, irritability) coincided with positive scraping results in most cases.

The low level of sanitary education among parents and educators is also a risk factor.

The data obtained emphasize the need to strengthen sanitary and hygienic measures in educational institutions and conduct regular preventive examinations.

Conclusion:

Enterobiasis remains a relevant infection among children in the Khorezm region, especially in younger age groups. The identified level of infection requires the adoption of preventive measures: regular examinations, sanitary and educational work, and the formation of personal hygiene skills in children and their parents are key measures in the fight against this disease.

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